

PHOTOCHEMICAL REACTIONS WITH SOME INORGANIC COLLOIDS AS ACTIVE AGENTS UNDER THE INFLUENCE OF LIGHT IN VARIOUS STATES OF POLARISATION PART I. TUNGSTIC ACID, MOLYBDIC ACID, CHROMIC TUNGSTATE, ETC. AS PHOTO ACTIVE REAGENTS ; OPTICAL PROPERTIES OF THESE SOLS ; CIRCULAR DICHROISM IN THE ULTRAVIOLET.

BY J. C. GHOSH, T. BANERJEE AND S. K. MUKHERJEE.

I N T R O D U C T I O N .

The most important photochemical synthesis in nature, the assimilation of carbon dioxide, takes place on the surface of the chloroplasts. Studies on the mechanism of photochemical reactions in heterogeneous systems, other than those involved in the processes, have been meagre. Such studies have an additional interest in that they may throw light on the process of asymmetric synthesis. The well known experiments of Weigert and Zocher on the anisotropy of thin layers of silver halide, irradiated with polarised light, promise interesting developments (Zocher and Coper, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1928, 132, 303, 313 ; Weigert, *Naturwiss.*, 1928, 16, 163 ; *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1929, 3B, 377, 389; 1929, 4B, 83).

Weigert discovered that a layer of photochloride on development after exposure to linearly polarised light has a weaker absorption for light with a direction of vibration parallel to that of the exciting beam, than for that with perpendicular vibrations (Weigert Effect, *Ann. Physik*, 1920, *iv*, 36, 681).

Analogous to this phenomenon, Zocher and Coper discovered that the illumination of silver chloride with circularly polarised light gave a layer of silver which showed simultaneously circular dichroism and circular double refraction. Cotton showed as early as 1893 that in the case of true solution of optically active substances, circular dichroism will be observed in the neighbourhood of an absorption band which is due to an electronic system that contributes to the optical rotation (Cotton effect). This discovery was followed up with remarkable ingenuity by Kuhn and co-workers, who were able to obtain optically active products by photochemical decomposition of solutions of ethyl α -bromopropionate and α -azide-propionic dimethylamide with circularly polarised light (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1930, 7 B, 292 ; *Naturwiss.*, 1929, 17, 227 ; 1930, 18, 183).

It is not unreasonable to expect that photochemical reactions taking

place on photo-active surface of micelles, where the molecules are arranged in a definite pattern, will show many peculiarities which are not observed in homogeneous photochemical reactions. The nature of these patterns and consequently the optical and surface properties of these micelles may undergo considerable variation if, during the aggregations of the constituent molecules to form the micelles, they are exposed to different types of polarised beams of light which they are capable of absorbing. It is because of this expectation that in our experiments, the reagents responsible for sol formation were in most cases exposed to radiations of different types, immediately after they are mixed together and attempts at purification from electrolytes by dialysis and other processes were avoided. Many sols are known where the micelles have been found to be needle-shaped or disc-shaped and have microcrystalline structure. It is probable that these sols, rather than those where the particles have amorphous structure and spherical shapes, will have stable characteristic orientation of the molecules during micelle formation and exhibit optical anisotropy. Our experimental results which are recorded in the following papers indicate unmistakably that in many cases circular dichroism in photo-active sol can be detected and in all such cases, a differential effect can be observed in the velocity of photochemical reactions when exposed to the same intensity of oppositely circularly polarised light.

Following up his pioneering work on micro-heterogeneous catalysis, Bredig and collaborators have demonstrated the parallelism between selective enzyme action and that of simple optically active catalysts. Bredig and Fiske found that the addition of hydrocyanic acid to benzaldehyde in presence of (+) quinine or (-) quinidine, followed by hydrolysis resulted in the formation of (+) or (-) mandelic acid respectively (*Biochem. Z.*, 1912, 46, 7). Bredig and Gerstner have found that dimethylamino groupings introduced into the structure of cotton fibre gave a catalyst which led to the formation of *l*-rotatory mandelonitrile (*Biochem. Z.*, 1932, 280, 414).

We believe that we have in our experiments been able to prepare by illumination with circularly polarised light micro-heterogeneous systems having asymmetric photo-active properties.

Vanadic Acid Sols.

It is well known that vanadium pentoxide is photosensitive ; it becomes black when exposed to light in contact with glycerol, benzaldehyde, etc.

When solutions of citric acid or tartaric acid are illuminated in presence of vanadium pentoxide, bluish green solutions are obtained (Renz, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1921, 4, 961). A thorough quantitative study of the mechanism of these reactions using monochromatic radiations and vanadic acid sol has not been made. This sol has got many peculiar properties. Freundlich and Leonhardt observed the phenomenon of streaming double refraction (*Koll.-Chem. Beih.*, 1915, 7, 172). According to Reinders this birefringence is not observed with freshly prepared colloidal solutions of vanadium pentoxide. On keeping, the double refraction is developed due to the formation of needle-shaped microcrystalline micelles (*Proc. Akad. Amsterdam*, 1916, 19, 189). Kruyt studied the Tyndall-effect of these sols in an electric field. This effect becomes very pronounced when the field is perpendicular to the luminous beams (*Verh. Akad. Amsterdam*, 1918, 18, 1625). Wiegner (*et al*) has given a concise and clear resumé of these properties (*Kolloid Z.*, 1922, 30, 145). Errera found that a sol, five years old containing 14 parts of vanadium pentoxide per thousand, had a specific inductive capacity of 400 (*Kolloid Z.*, 1922, 31, 59; 1923, 32, 157, 372). Lange studied the polarisation of the Tyndall light from the sol and concluded that the particles were not spherical in shape (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1928, 132, 21). Zocher (*et al*) have studied the thixotropic properties of the sol and noticed that these sols within certain range of concentrations separate into two phases, one isotropic and dilute, the other anisotropic and concentrated (*Kolloid Z.*, 1927, 41, 220). He has also described the various methods for determining the anisotropy of colloidal particles (*Kolloid Z.*, 1925, 37, 347).

The application of "Azimuthblende" to dark ground illumination enabled Szegvari to study the regional orientation of needle-shaped micelles, and he concludes that "Die fast ausschliesslich nadelförmigen Teilchen des Vanadium pentoxide soles sind gebietweise untereinander parallel orientiert"..... "Die dauernde Doppelbrechung, die diese sole in makroskopischen Schichten zeigen ist auch verständlich.....Eine so einmahl erzeugte makroskopische Orientierung der an sich mikroskopisch orientierten Gebiete wird nach Aufhören des sie verursachenden Geschwindigkeitsgefalles bestehen bleiben" (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1924, 112, 300, 304).

Tungstic Acid Sols.

Wasiliewa observed that when a colloidal solution of tungstic acid is illuminated in presence of dextroses, formaldehyde, etc., a blue solution due

to reduced tungstic acid is obtained (*Z. Wiss. Phot.*, 1913, 12, 1; *cf.*, also Ghosh and co-workers, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 231, 975). Ghosh and Bhattacharyya have studied the effect of ageing of sols of tungstic acid and molybdic acid on their capacity for the photoreduction of ethyl alcohol (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 720).

It was observed long ago by Graham that when a dilute solution of hydrochloric acid is added to a solution of sodium tungstate until the liquid becomes acid, a colloidal solution of tungstic acid is formed. Huttig and Kurre (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1922, 122, 44) from a study of dehydration curves deduced that yellow tungstic acid prepared from a boiling solution is a compound H_2WO_4 , but that the white product prepared in the cold is a colloid behaving as a conglomerate of tungsten trioxide particles arranged in an irregular manner. Jander and Winkel (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1930, 149, 97) found that the normal tungstate exists in solution between p_H 6.5 and 14; between p_H 1.5 and 5, tungstic acid exists in polymerised colloidal form.

The shape of the micelles of tungstic acid have not been fully studied. Wiegner states that they are flat and disc shaped (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1931, 50, 110 T).

Dumanski and Djatschkowski (*Kolloid Z.*, 1929, 48, 49) conclude "Die allmähliche Komplexation von weinsauren Komplexen durch Eintritt von WO_3 Radikalen führt zunächst zu grobdispersen Kolloiden, bei weiterer Sättigung aber zu hochdispersen Kolloid-systemen. Die untersuchten Kolloid-systeme, besitzen thixotrope Eigenschaften und die Gele besitzen such photo-chemische Empfindlichkeit." Freundlich and Kross (*Kolloid Z.*, 1930, 52, 46) in their studies on titanium dioxide sols observe that these sols are thixotropic but ultramicroscopic investigation does not reveal any deviation from spherical shape. The strong depolarisation of the Tyndall light is, however, in agreement with the general expectation that concentrated thixotropic sols should exhibit positive streaming double refraction. Tungstic acid sols, which also exhibit thixotropy may, therefore, be expected to possess optical anisotropy.

Molybdic Acid Sol.

Graham obtained a colloidal solution of molybdic acid by the addition of hydrochloric acid to a solution of sodium molybdate. According to Britton and German who carried out electrometric titration of solutions of sodium molybdate with hydrochloric acid, an inflexion point is observed

at p_H 4.8, below which a highly ionised polymolybdic acid exists (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 2154).

Dumanski and co-workers studied the conductivity and freezing point lowering of solutions obtained by adding acids to sodium molybdate. The colloidal molybdic acid was not coagulated either by cooling or heating and had a mol. wt. of the order of 1200 (*Kolloid Z.*, 1926, 38, 208). Wohler and Engels conclude that depending on conditions of experiment, molybdic acid can be obtained in the colloidal state. On acidifying, the molybdic acid polymerises, but the particles are so small that the solution on prolonged dialysis diffuses through a parchment (*Koll.-Chem. Beih.*, 1910, 1, 454). Ghosh and Bhattacharyya have studied the photochemical reduction of colloidal molybdic acid by ethyl alcohol (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 717).

The authors are not aware of any investigation which had for its objects the determination of the shape of the particles of molybdic acid sol.

S. Ghosh and N. R. Dhar (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1929, 184, 135; 1930, 190, 425) observe "dass frisch aus Ammoniummolybdat und Salzsäure hergestelltes Sol von Molybdänsäure grosse Mengen Molybdansäure molekular gelöst enthält, welche sich allmählich zu grösseren Molekeln und Kolloidteilchen vereinigen und schliesslich ausgefällt werden, wenn die zusammenballung fortschreitet."

Uranic Acid Sol.

Diachkovoski (*British Chemical Abstracts*, 1927, 1137), has studied the properties of uranic acid sols. The velocity in electric field corresponds with a negative charge of 1.984×10^{-8} E.S.U.

Aloy and Valdignie (*Compt. rend.*, 1923, 176, 1229) observed that if a mixture of uranium salt, dextrose and methylene blue in solution is exposed to light, the dextrose is oxidised and methylene blue reduced, the uranium playing the rôle of photocatalyst.

Chromium Hydroxide Sol.

A very large number of investigations have been carried out with chromium hydroxide sol, since it was first obtained by Graham by peptising the freshly precipitated oxide with chromic chloride and subsequent dialysis. A positive hydrosol is obtained in this way. On the other hand

the green sol obtained by adding excess of alkali to a solution of chromic salt is negative. The structure of the micelles has been studied by Wintgen and Lowenthal, Wintgen and Kuhn (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1929, 109, 391; 1928, 138, 149). who found that the following equation holds good,

$$\text{Log } A_L = -0.707 \log \frac{[Cl]}{[Cr]} + 44$$

where A_L is equivalent aggregation

Chromium Tungstate Sol. Our knowledge of this sol is meagre. Its method of preparation has been described in a paper by Banerjee (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 15, 59).

B. GENERAL EXPERIMENTAL ARRANGEMENT FOR THE STUDY OF PHOTOCHEMICAL REACTIONS IN POLARISED LIGHT.

The experimental arrangement is described in Fig. 1. The source of light was a point source quartz mercury lamp which was run from a battery of 30 volts. An ammeter in circuit and a variable external resistance were used to keep the strength of current constant at value between 2 and 2.6 amperes.

The following filters were used for isolating monochromatic radiations:—

For	313 $\mu\mu$	} Chance Bros. ultraviolet filter (1 cm.).
	334 $\mu\mu$	
	366 $\mu\mu$	Schott and Gen ultraviolet filter no. 312.
	436 $\mu\mu$	} Zeiss monochromats.
	579 $\mu\mu$	

In the case of red light, a thousand c.p. point-o-lite Ediswan lamp was used with suitable filters.

Light from the lamp was rendered parallel by a quartz lens placed at its focal distance from the lamp and passed into the reaction vessel kept inside a double jacketed box through a window of fused quartz plate. The temperature was kept constant within 0.1° by circulating water from a thermostat through the annular space of the box. The reaction vessel was a rectangular stoppered cell made of plane parallel plates of fused transparent silica. No cement was used, the rectangular joints being fused to one another. The closed stopper which was very well ground into a circular aperture in the thick top-plate of the reaction cell was in some

cases replaced by a hollow stopper with inlet and exit tubes for bubbling pure nitrogen. The intensity of incident radiation was varied by using quartz lenses of different focal lengths. The method of measuring intensities actually absorbed by the reaction mixture consisted in first observing the deflection in a Moll galvanometer with a Moll surface thermopile covered with a quartz window and placed immediately behind the reaction cell which contained only water. The deflection was next noted when the cell was filled with the reacting mixture. The difference gave the quantity of radiant energy absorbed by the reacting system. The thermopile recording system was frequently calibrated by means of a standard incandescent lamp tested by the National Bureau of Standards, Washington. The scattering power for light was found to be very small in the case of the sols, which we have studied (*vide* Part VIII*).

FIG 1.

Description and the Working Principle of the Polarising Apparatus especially Constructed for the Purpose.

Plane polarised light was obtained by interposing in the path of the parallel beam a prism (N) of the Glans type supplied by Bernard Halle.

This was fitted with a graduated circle (G) and the rotation of the prism can be read from a vernier (Z) attached to the stand.

The circularly polarised light was obtained with the help of the polarising prism and a quartz quarter wave plate (Q), specially constructed for the purpose by Carl Zeiss. The latter was of the type for which the path of retardation between two principal components can be adjusted to the exactly $\lambda/4$ for any given wave-length by means of a calibrated rotating drum (D), (R is the pointer which reads the wave-length on the drum), which slides the component parts of the quartz combinations with respect to each other. The direction of vibration of light transmitted by the polarising prism was determined by reflecting it at very near Brewsterian angle from a plane glass plate.

The axis of retardation of the $\lambda/4$ combination was determined by combining it with a Fresnel's Rhomb so that the principal directions of the former may be in the plane of incidence for the latter, and perpendicular to it respectively. When introduced between crossed nicols, if they restore the light strongly, the axis of retardation for the $\lambda/4$ plate is the same as for the Fresnel's Rhomb. Otherwise, they are at right angles to each other.

$A_1 A'_1, A_2 A'_2$ are the principal axes of the $\lambda/4$ plate. Let light be incident from below in the plane of the paper, when $A_2 A'_2$ is the axis of retardation, the rotation is anticlockwise or *dextro*-rotatory and corresponds to right handed circular polarisation or *d*-circular polarisation. On the other hand, $A_1 A'_1$ is the axis of retardation, the emerged light is left-handed circularly or *l*-circularly polarised light (*vide* fig. 2.)

FIG 2.

C. MEASUREMENT OF CIRCULAR DICHROISM.

Kuhn and Braun (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1930, 8B, 446) have developed a method for the determination of circular dichroism in the ultraviolet based on the principle that the axial relations of an elliptically polarised beam of light are changed on passing through a medium which has different absorption coefficients for *d*- and *l*-circularly polarised light. "Durch eine

Halbschatten-vorrichtung wird erreicht, dass die eine Hälfte des Gesichtsfeldes vor dem Eintritt in das absorbierende Medium in veränderlichem und messbarem Mass Schwach rechts-, die andere in davonverschiedenem Mass linkselliptisches light liefert. Durcheinem Analysator werden die Bedingungen festgestellt, under denen das Achsenverhältniss der beiden aus dem absorbierendem Medium austretenden Strahlen jeglichen Betrag erhalt."

On a similar principle Bruhat has developed a method for measuring circular dichroism in the visible (*Bull. Soc. chim.*, 1930, 47, 251).

Our experimental arrangement for measuring circular dichroism in the ultraviolet is given below :—

An End-on-quartz mercury lamp (S), run from a battery of 220 volts at constant current is focussed on slit S_1 of Hilger Larger Aperture Monochromator D 41, by the quartz condenser (F 278) L (vide Fig. 3). Monochromatic radiation passing through slit S_2 was converted into an approximately parallel beam by the cylindrical lens L_2 of fused quartz and focussed on the plate in the camera K. Immediately in front of this was placed the Wollaston prism Q, which gave two beams with a separation of 2.5 mm. and polarised at right angles to each other. P is the $\lambda/4$ plate manufactured by Carl Zeiss. The two beams, circularly polarised in opposite direction, were now passed through an absorption cell C of fused transparent quartz (1 cm. square $\times$ 2mm.). Between the lens L, and slit S_1 was fitted a graduated rotating sector (Leiss) mounted on the spindle of a motor.

FIG. 3.

Ilford process plates were used in the camera; by a rack and pinion arrangement, fitted to the carrier, fourteen impressions could be taken one above the other on the same photographic plate. Each plate contained nine impressions with water in the cell for nine different readings of the rotating sector, time-interval being the same in all cases. The remaining five impressions were taken with the cell filled with the sol matured under five different conditions. The time of exposure was regulated with an accurate metronome.

A graph was drawn by plotting log sector reading (which is proportional to $\log I$, I being the intensity of the transmitted light) against blackening* of the corresponding impression on the plate. Fig 4 gives the nature of the graph obtained. The time of exposure with the sol in the absorption cell was so chosen that with full aperture (180°) of the rotating sector, blackening of the impressions obtained always remained in the portion of the curve AB, where it was a straight line.

The exposed plates were developed (in complete darkness) with 'Rodinal' diluted 20 times with distilled water at 18° for 5 minutes. For uniform development the bath was well placed on a shaking machine.

The plate after fixing was washed for an hour with distilled water at 18° by repeatedly changing water in the dish. The plate was dried at ordinary temperature in a large dust-free glass chamber.

The blackening of the image was measured with Zeiss photo-electric microphotometer, kept inside an air-conditioned dust-free room of low relative humidity.

The sols used were tungstic acid sol, chromic tungstate sol, vanadic acid sol, molybdic acid sol, chromic hydroxide sol and uranic acid sol. Their methods of preparation are given in Parts II, IV, VI, IX† of this paper and in a paper by Banerjee (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 14, , 59).

After mixing together the sol-forming reagents or after dialysis as the case may be, each sol was subjected to the following maturing treatment.

- (1) Sol matured in the dark for a definite period.
- (2) Sol matured in unpolarised light ($366\mu\mu$) for a definite period.
- (3) Sol matured in plane-polarised light ($366\mu\mu$) for a definite period.
- (4) Sol matured in *l*-circularly polarised light ($366\mu\mu$) for a definite period.

* Blackening is defined by $D_0 - d_1/D_0$, where D_0 is the deflection of the electrometer of the Zeiss microphotometer from its position when only the clean plate is in the path of the beam and d_1 is the deflection when a spectral line intercepts the beam.

† Part IX of this series will be published in the next issue of this Journal.

(5) Sol matured in *d*-circularly polarised light ($366 \mu\mu$) for a definite period.

For the same sol, the time of maturing was the same in all cases.

A graph was prepared for the nine impressions of each plate with water in the absorption cell by plotting log sector reading (which is proportional to the intensity of transmitted light) against the corresponding blackening. From the graph, the log intensities of transmitted light, when sols matured under the above five conditions were in the cell, were found out from the corresponding values of the blackening of the remaining five impressions on the same plate.

From the values of log sector reading, actual value of absorption coefficient of a sol can obviously be calculated if the angle of opening corresponding to each sector reading is known. 100 Divisions of the sector correspond to 180° .

FIG. 4.

The results are summarised below.

Log sector reading (*d*) indicates log sector reading when the incident light was *d*-circularly polarised. Log sector reading (*l*) indicates log sector reading when the incident light was *l*-circularly polarised. Absorption coefficient in *d*-circularly polarised light is indicated by A_d . Absorption coefficient in *l*-circularly polarised light is indicated by A_l .

TABLE I,
Moxybdic Acid sol.

Sector reading.	Log sector reading.	D_0	$D_0 - d_1$	$D_0 - d_2$	$\frac{D_0 - d_1}{D_0}$	$\frac{D_0 - d_2}{D_0}$
13	1'1139	63'9	36'0	26'9	0'563	0'421
12	1'0794	63'0	34'0	25'7	0'540	0'408
11	1'0414	61'5	29'8	20'6	0'485	0'335
10	1'0000	63'7	28'2	19'8	0'443	0'311
9	0'9544	63'0	24'5	16'2	0'390	0'237
8	0'9031	65'0	20'2	13'2	0'311	0'203
7	0'8451	64'3	15'6	9'5	0'243	0'148
6	0'7782	65'3	10'8	5'5	0'171	0'087
5	0'6990	61'5	7'2	3'9	0'113	0'061

A. With water in the cell.

TABLE I (contd.).

B. With sol in the cell.

Conc. of molybdic acid sol (in terms of molybdate equiv.) = 0.025M.
 $\bar{d}$ (thickness of the cell) = 0.2 cm.

Nature of light in which the sol was matured for 10 hrs. immediately after mixing the reagents.	D_0	$D_0 - d_1$	$D_0 - d_2$	$\frac{D_0 - d_1}{D_0}$	$\frac{D_0 - d_2}{D_0}$	Log sector reading (β).	Absorp. coefficient (A_1).	Absorp. coefficient (A_2).	Anisotropy factor $\beta = \frac{A_1 - A_2}{\frac{1}{2}(A_1 + A_2)}$
l-Circularly polarised	64.3	22.6	16.1	0.351	0.250	0.940	5.255	5.300	-0.0085
d-Circularly polarised	62.8	27.2	19.7	0.433	0.314	1.002	4.97	4.99	-0.0040
Plane polarised	64.3	25.9	17.3	0.403	0.269	0.972	5.17	5.14	+0.0038
Unpolarised	64.3	22.3	14.2	0.347	0.221	0.930	5.39	5.35	+0.0075
kept in the dark	64.8	26.3	17.9	0.390	0.276	0.971	5.14	5.148	-0.0009

TABLE II.

Chromic hydroxide sol.

A. With water in the cell.

Sector reading.	Log sector reading.	D_0 .	$D_1 - d_1$.	$D_2 - d_2$.	$\frac{D_0 - d_1}{D_0}$	$\frac{D_0 - d_2}{D_0}$
13	1.1139	60.3	37.0	30.8	0.614	0.511
12	1.0792	60.0	35.0	28.0	0.583	0.467
11	1.0454	57.5	33.0	26.0	0.574	0.445
10	1.0000	60.3	29.7	23.1	0.493	0.383
9	0.9542	59.4	26.8	20.5	0.450	0.345
8	0.9031	61.6	26.2	19.7	0.425	0.320
7	0.8451	61.3	19.3	13.9	0.315	0.226
6	0.7782	60.0	13.2	8.9	0.220	0.148
5	0.6990	54.5	10.0	6.4	0.190	0.121

TABLE II (contd.).

B. With sol in the cell.

Conc. of chromic hydroxide sol (in terms of chromic equiv.) = 0.02M.

d (thickness of the cell) = 0.2 cm.

Nature of light in which the sol was matured for 10 hrs. after dialysis.	D_0 .	$D_0 - d_1$.	$D_0 - d_2$.	$\frac{D_0 - d_1}{D_0}$.	$\frac{D_0 - d_2}{D_0}$.	Log sector reading (θ).	Absorp. coefficient (A_1).	Absorp. coefficient (A_2).	Anisotropy factor $g = \frac{A_1 - A_2}{\frac{1}{2}(A_1 + A_2)}$
I-Circularly polarised	59.7	23.5	18.8	0.394	0.315	0.924	5.38	5.42	-0.0074
II-Circularly polarised	60.6	26.2	20.6	0.432	0.340	0.949	5.24	5.26	-0.0030
Plane polarised	60.8	26.8	21.3	0.441	0.350	0.957	5.19	5.21	-0.0030
Unpolarised	61.8	24.7	20.0	0.400	0.324	0.921	5.35	5.36	-0.0086
Kept in the dark	59.2	23.7	18.7	0.400	0.316	0.921	5.37	5.36	-0.0040

TABLE III.
Uranic acid sol.

A. With water in the cell.

Sector reading.	Log sector reading.	D_4	$D_0 - d_1$.	$D_0 - d_2$.	$\frac{D_0 - d_1}{D_0}$.	$\frac{D_0 - d_2}{D_0}$.
13	1.1139	60.3	32.7	26.4	0.542	0.438
12	1.0792	61.3	32.6	25.8	0.532	0.421
11	1.0414	60.1	28.3	22.9	0.471	0.381
10	1.0000	60.6	27.1	20.8	0.447	0.343
9	0.9542	61.2	21.0	15.0	0.343	0.245
8	0.9031	61.7	20.0	14.1	0.324	0.229
7	0.8451	59.5	12.6	8.5	0.210	0.143
6	0.7782	60.6	9.4	6.0	0.155	0.097
5	0.6990	59.8	5.3	3.5	0.0886	0.0585

TABLE III (contd.).

B. With sol in the cell.

Conc. of sol (as uranic acid) = 0.0183M.

d (thickness of the cell) = 0.2 cm.

Nature of light in which the sol was matured for 10 hrs. immediately after preparation.	D_0	$D_0 - d_1$	$D_0 - d_2$	$\frac{D_0 - d_1}{D_0}$	$\frac{D_0 - d_2}{D_0}$	Log sector reading (θ).	Absorp. coeff. (A_1).	Absorp. coeff. (A_2).	Anisotropy factor $g = \frac{A_1 - A_2}{\frac{1}{2}(A_1 + A_2)}$
$\perp$ Circularly polarised	59.0	29.1	13.6	0.324	0.231	0.936	5.35	5.32	+0.0036
d -Circularly polarised	60.0	24.1	17.6	0.402	0.293	0.984	5.12	5.08	+0.0078
Plane polarised	59.0	18.6	13.2	0.315	0.224	0.928	5.38	5.36	+0.0037
Unpolarised	61.8	23.9	17.2	0.381	0.274	0.972	5.16	5.14	+0.0039
Kept in the dark	61.4	22.2	16.6	0.362	0.270	0.962	5.21	5.19	+0.0038

TABLE IV.
Tungstic acid sol.

A. With water in the cell.						
Sector reading.	Log sector reading.	D_4 .	$D_0 - d_1$.	$D_0 - d_2$.	$\frac{D_0 - d_1}{D_0}$.	$\frac{D_0 - d_2}{D_0}$.
33	1'1139	55'0	23'0	21'2	0'455	0'389
32	1'0782	61'5	24'2	20'0	0'394	0'326
31	1'0414	61'5	23'6	19'1	0'384	0'311
30	1'0000	60'5	21'0	15'7	0'347	0'260
9	0'9542	55'0	15'8	12'2	0'287	0'222
8	0'0031	55'5	14'2	10'3	0'256	0'187
7	0'8451	57'3	11'6	8'2	0'202	0'143
6	0'7782	54'4	8'4	4'2	0'154	0'077
5	0'6990	59'0	7'0	3'9	0'110	0'066

TABLE IV (contd.).

B. With sol in the cell.

Conc. of tungstic acid sol (in terms of tungstate equivalent) = 0.0125M. $d = 0.2$ cm.

Nature of light in which the sol was matured for 6 hrs. immediately after mixing the reagents.	D_0	$D_0 - d_1$	$D_0 - d_2$	$\frac{D_0 - d_1}{D_0}$	$\frac{D_0 - d_2}{D_0}$	Log sector reading (d).	Absorp. coeff. (A ₁).	Absorp. coeff. (A ₂).	Anisotropy factor $g = \frac{A_1 - A_2}{\frac{1}{2}(A_1 + A_2)}$.	
l-Circularly polarised	60.8	20.0	13.6	0.329	0.224	0.982	0.954	5.23	5.09	+0.0271
d-Circularly polarised	45.5	15.6	12.8	0.343	0.281	0.996	1.018	4.91	5.02	-0.0221
Plane polarised	43.6	16.2	13.1	0.372	0.300	1.026	1.034	4.83	4.87	+0.0082
Unpolarised	51.6	15.1	10.8	0.293	0.209	0.942	0.936	5.32	5.29	-0.0056
Kept in the dark	50.6	17.4	13.2	0.344	0.261	0.998	1.000	5.01	5.001	+0.0001

TABLE V.
Vanadic acid sol.

A. With water in the cell.							
Sector reading.	Log sector reading.	D_0	D_0-d_1	D_0-d_4	$\frac{D_0-d_1}{D_0}$	$\frac{D_0-d_4}{D_0}$	$\frac{D_0-d_4}{D_0-d_1}$
13	1.1139	61.0	34.8	26.4	0.570	0.433	
12	1.0792	64.7	33.0	25.2	0.510	0.389	
11	1.0414	52.0	26.1	21.3	0.453	0.344	
10	1.0000	63.1	27.0	18.9	0.428	0.300	
9	0.9542	63.3	23.8	15.5	0.376	0.245	
8	0.9031	61.2	18.3	12.5	0.299	0.204	
7	0.8451	61.2	13.5	8.6	0.221	0.141	
6	0.7782	59.9	9.3	5.9	0.155	0.099	
5	0.6990	57.5	6.0	3.8	0.104	0.066	

TABLE V (contd.).

B. With sol in the cell.

Conc. of vanadic acid sol (in terms of vanadate equiv.) = 0.0025M. $d = 0.2$ cm.

Nature of light in which the sol was measured for 10 hrs. immediately after mixing the reagents.	D_0	D_0-d_1	D_0-d_2	$\frac{D_0-d_1}{D_0}$	$\frac{D_0-d_2}{D_0}$	Log sector reading	Absorp. coeff. (A_1)	Anisotropy factor $g = \frac{A_1 - A_2}{\frac{1}{2}(A_1 + A_2)}$		
				(d).	(β).		(A_1)			
l-Circularly polarised	63.0	17.9	10.9	0.284	0.173	0.908	0.876	5.62	5.46	+0.0089
d-Circularly polarised	59.7	15.7	11.3	0.263	0.189	0.888	0.894	5.53	5.36	-0.0054
Plane polarised	55.0	15.0	10.3	0.273	0.187	0.896	0.892	5.54	5.52	+0.0036
Unpolarised	62.7	14.8	10.3	0.236	0.164	0.866	0.860	5.70	5.67	+0.0053
Kept in the dark	65.0	16.1	10.0	0.233	0.145	0.858	0.848	5.76	5.71	+0.0087

TABLE VI.

Chromic tungstate.

A. With water in the cell,

Sector reading.	Log sector reading.	D_0 .	D_0-d_1 .	D_0-d_2 .	$\frac{D_0-d_1}{D_0}$.	$\frac{D_0-d_2}{D_0}$.
13	1.1139	57.8	39.4	33.8	0.682	0.585
12	1.0792	60.0	38.2	32.1	0.637	0.535
11	1.0414	60.2	36.2	30.6	0.601	0.508
10	1.0000	60.6	34.3	28.1	0.566	0.464
9	0.9542	61.9	32.2	25.8	0.520	0.417
8	0.9031	59.9	30.3	23.1	0.506	0.386
7	0.8451	59.4	25.6	18.8	0.431	0.317
6	0.7782	60.0	19.3	14.4	0.322	0.2400
5	0.6990	60.2	13.8	10.0	0.229	0.166

TABLE VI (contd.).

B. With sol in the cell.

Conc. of chromic tungstate (in terms of tungstate equiv.) = 0.02M.

d (thickness of the cell) = 0.2 cm.

Nature of light in which the sol was matured for 10 hrs. immediately after mixing the reagents.	D_0	$D_1 - \phi_1$	$D_0 - \phi_0$	$\frac{D_0 - \phi_1}{D_0}$	$\frac{D_0 - \phi_0}{D_0}$	Log sector reading	Absorp. coeff.	Anisotropy factor	
						(d).	(A.).	$g = \frac{A_1 - A_2}{\frac{1}{2}(A_1 - A_2)}$	
d-Circularly polarised	...	61.4	18.7	13.2	0.256	0.215	0.750	6.44	-0.0284
Plane polarised	..	39.3	15.3	10.3	0.358	0.174	0.710	6.45	+0.0077
Unpolarised	...	58.0	20.6	16.2	0.355	0.279	0.806	5.97	+0.0017
Kept in the dark	...	66.3	20.5	16.9	0.340	0.280	0.798	5.97	-0.0067

The small difference in the values of absorption coefficients for monochromatic light in the same state of polarisation exhibited by the sols (containing the same equivalent of light absorbing constituents per litre) is due to the fact that in the formation of colloids from the required ingredients, the mass and size of the colloidal particles could not be controlled to remain exactly the same in all cases.

In our results the experimental error is such that the anisotropy factor of the order of 0.008 has no significance. The anisotropy factor shown by molecular solutions investigated by Kuhn and co-workers varied from 0.005 to 0.04.

For tungstic acid sol, matured in *l*-circularly polarised light for 6 hours, we observe a *positive* anisotropy factor, equal to 0.027 and for sol matured in *d*-circularly polarised light, a *negative* anisotropy factor of the value of 0.0221.

For chromic tungstate acid sol, matured in *d*-circularly polarised light for 10 hours, a negative anisotropy factor, equal to 0.0284 was observed.

For vanadic acid sol, matured in *l*-circularly polarised light for 10 hours, a *positive* anisotropy factor, of the value of 0.029 was observed. In the case of vanadic acid sol, matured in *d*-circularly polarised light for 10 hours, the *negative* anisotropy factor, (equal to 0.0054), though small, indicates some positive significance and it can easily be expected that on maturing the sol in *d*-circularly polarised light for a longer period, it might be possible to induce anisotropy to a greater extent.

In the cases of molybdic acid sol, chromic hydroxide sol and uranic acid sol, the values of anisotropy factor are within experimental error and have no significance.

Following are the microphotographs of the plates taken in connection with the experiments on tungstic acid sol (*vide* Table IV).

CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
DACCА UNIVERSITY
RAMNA, DACCА.

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PLATE 2.

With water in the absorption cell at sector reading 6,

PLATE 1.

With sol. pre-excited in *l*-circularly polarised light, in the absorption cell at sector reading 100.

PLATE 4.

With sol. pre-excited in plane polarised light in the absorption cell at sector reading 100.

PLATE 3.

With sol. kept in the dark for 6 hours, in the absorption cell at sector reading 100.

PLATE 6.

With SO_2 pre-excited in d -circularly polarised light, in the cell at sector reading 100.

PLATE 8.

With water in the absorption cell at sector reading 11.

PLATE 5.

With SO_2 pre-excited in unpolarised light, in the absorption cell at sector reading 100.

PLATE 7.

With water in the absorption cell at sector reading 12.

PLATE 10.

With water in the absorption cell at sector reading 9.

PLATE 9.

With water in the absorption cell at sector reading 10

PLATE 12.

With water in the absorption cell at sector reading 7.

PLATE 11.

With water in the absorption cell at sector reading 8.

